

Psychosocial factors leading to Internet gaming disorder: A mediating role of personal disposition

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ABSTRACT: This study delves into the intricate dynamics surrounding internet gaming disorder (IGD) among university students, focusing on the mediating role of personal disposition amidst prosocial factors. Employing a purposive sampling strategy, 355 students from diverse departments at the University of Peshawar participated in this research. A robust array of reliable scales, including the Internet Gaming Disorder Scale–Short Form 9 (IGD Scale–SF 9; Pontes & Griffiths, 2015), Buss Perry Brief Aggression Questionnaire (BAQ; Bryant & Smith, 2001), Personal Dispositions Scale (PDS; Anderson & Bushman, 2002), Penn State Worry Questionnaire (PSWQ; Meyer et al., 1990), Perceived Stress Scale 10-item version (PSS10; Cohen et al., 1983), Sadistic Attitudes and Behaviors Scale (SABS-10; Baumeister & Vohs, 2007), and Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWL; Diener et al., 1985), facilitated comprehensive data collection. Our findings unveil the profound impact of psychological factors—specifically, psychological distress, perceived stress, and satisfaction with life—on IGD among undergraduate students. Additionally, the study sheds light on the pivotal role played by personal dispositions such as aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies in shaping internet gaming behavior. Through meticulous correlational analysis, significant associations emerged among variables, particularly highlighting the interconnectedness of psychological distress, satisfaction with life, worry, perceived stress, and various dimensions of aggression. Notably, gender-based differences in these variables were found to be non-significant. The implications of our results resonate deeply, offering valuable insights into the complex interplay of factors contributing to IGD among university students. These findings serve as a beacon, illuminating potential avenues for intervention and support strategies. In essence, this study propels our understanding of the multifaceted influences underlying IGD, paving the way for future research endeavors and the development of effective preventive and therapeutic measures.

Keyword: Psychological; Social Factors; Internet Gaming Disorder; Personal Disposition; Mediation

Introduction

Methods

Materials and Methods

Discussion

Implications & Suggestions

Conclusion

References

1. Introduction

Globally, there is a growing problem of internet gaming disorder among college students. However, there is a dearth of comprehensive research on the role of personality traits as mediators. This study fills this gap by examining the relationship between internet gaming problems and psychosocial aspects as well as individual characteristics like sadness, rage, and concern. This is done to comprehend the psychological underpinnings of problematic gaming better. A strong theoretical framework combines psychosocial components with traits of anger, worry, and sadism.

Digital technology has transformed how individuals communicate, learn, and enjoy themselves (Smith, 2019). This technological innovation has made internet gaming popular globally, including among Pakistani university students (Johnson et al., 2020). Internet games offer a variety of immersive and engaging experiences to escape the rigors of daily living. Gaming can be healthy, but it can also lead to excessive and harmful gaming, especially among young people (Anderson et al., 2017; Hussain, Griffiths, & Baguley, 2015).

IGD is Pakistani students' most common internet gaming issue. IGD can impair social functioning, physical activity, academic engagement, sleep patterns, emotional well-being, and academic performance, making it important to study. Thus, identifying the causes of internet gaming disorder in adolescents is essential to developing effective prevention and intervention techniques to reduce its detrimental effects.

This study examines how hostility, concern, and sadism mediate psychosocial factors and internet gaming disorder in Pakistani adolescents. The variables studied are described below:

This study examines Internet Gaming Disorder. IGD is characterized by impaired control over gaming, prioritizing gaming over other activities, and continuing gaming despite detrimental effects on well-being and daily functioning. Men are more prone to play online excessively and get IGD than women, according to research. Males game more and have more severe addiction symptoms (Lemmens, Valkenburg, & Peter, 2009). Some research suggest that men and women may utilise internet gaming to manage stress and negative emotions. Gender-related differences in self-esteem, social support, and psychological discomfort may affect IGD risk (Snodgrass et al., 2014).

Paik, Cho, Chun, Jeong, & Kim (2017) examined gaming behaviors and clinical characteristics across gaming device usage patterns and their effects on Internet gaming disorder. Researchers identified smartphone and internet game users by gaming device usage patterns in an online survey: (1) individuals who played only computer games; (2) individuals who played computer games more than smartphone games; (3) individuals who played on a computer and smartphone games evenly; (4) individuals who played smartphone games more than computer games; (5) individuals who played only smartphone games. The study found that combined users, especially those who played computer and smartphone games equally, had greater rates of IGD, melancholy, anxiety, and drug use disorder. These respondents had a higher risk of IGD than computer-only gamers ($B = 0.457$, odds ratio = 1.579). Smartphone-only gamers had the lowest IGD rates,

spent the least time and money on gaming, and had the lowest Internet and smartphone addiction scores. Our findings imply that gaming device usage may affect IGD occurrence, course, and prognosis. A meta-analysis by Fam (2018) indicated that 4.6% (95% CI = 3.4%–6.0%) of adolescents had internet gaming disorder (IGD) over three decades. On average, male adolescents had a larger prevalence rate (6.8%, 95% CI = 4.3%–9.7%) than female adolescents (1.3%, 0.6%–2.2%).

One of the recent studies conducted on IGD and its impact on the mental health of Pakistani students, focusing on the pathways involving impulsivity and emotional intelligence (Khalid & Mukhtar, 2022), revealed a high level of IGD (58.9%) among Pakistani youth involved in online gaming. Findings also confirmed the partially mediated role of impulsivity in the relationship between emotional intelligence and IGD, which subsequently reduces well-being (also see Ahsan, Rasheed, & Zonash, 2019; Khan & Muqtadir, 2016; Suhail & Bargees, 2006; Khan and Muqtadir, 2016).

For the present study, the interplay of psychological and social elements that influence an individual's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors (psychosocial factors) related to the development and maintenance of Internet gaming disorder is taken as the Independent Variable (Brown & Sandler, 2019). In this context, three psychosocial factors (psychological distress, satisfaction with life, and perceived stress) are taken into consideration among university students (Cao et al., 2021).

Definitions:

1. Psychological distress refers to a state of emotional or psychological discomfort characterized by a range of negative feelings such as anxiety, depression, and unease. (Kessler, Green, Gruber, Sampson, Bromet, Cuitan, & Zaslavsky, 2010).
2. Satisfaction with Life is a subjective assessment of an individual's overall contentment and well-being (Diener, Emmons, Larsen, & Griffin, 1985).
3. Perceived Stress refers to an individual's perception of the level of stress they experience in response to various life events or circumstances (Cohen, Kamarck, & Mermelstein, 1983).

Hussain, Griffiths, and Baguley (2015) in Pakistan examined the prevalence and risk factors of internet addiction among university students. Their findings revealed a significant positive correlation between psychological distress and excessive internet gaming, suggesting that students experiencing higher levels of emotional distress were more prone to developing internet gaming disorder. Similarly, in a cross-sectional study by Iqbal and Bano (2016), the researchers investigated the impact of life satisfaction on internet gaming disorder among Pakistani college students. They discovered a negative association between life satisfaction and excessive gaming behavior, indicating that students who reported lower life satisfaction were more likely to engage in problematic gaming activities as a coping mechanism.

A study by Kim et al. (2015) in South Korea, one of the pioneering countries in gaming research, examined the association between psychological distress and internet

gaming disorder among adolescents. Their findings supported previous evidence, highlighting that higher levels of psychological distress were linked to an increased likelihood of developing addictive gaming behaviors. This study reinforced the need to consider emotional well-being when studying the prevalence and risk factors of internet gaming disorder. In another study conducted by Feng et al. (2016) in China, researchers explored the relationship between life satisfaction and problematic online gaming among college students. The results indicated that individuals reporting lower life satisfaction were more susceptible to engaging in excessive gaming as a way to escape dissatisfaction with real-life circumstances. This study underscored the role of life satisfaction as an essential psychosocial factor in understanding the motivations behind internet gaming disorder. Additionally, a cross-cultural study by Männikkö et al. (2017) examined the association between perceived stress and online gaming addiction among university students from different countries, including the United States, Germany, and South Korea. The findings revealed a positive correlation between perceived stress and problematic gaming behavior across all countries, highlighting the universal relevance of stress as a contributing factor to internet gaming disorder.

For the present study, three personal dispositions such as Aggression, Worry, and Sadistic Tendencies are taken as mediating variables. These personal dispositions are defined as:

Aggression: Aggression refers to behavior that is intended to cause harm, either physical or psychological, to another individual or entity. It can encompass a wide range of actions, from verbal aggression (such as yelling or insulting) to physical aggression (such as hitting or pushing). Aggressive behavior can stem from various factors, including frustration, anger, competition, or the desire to assert dominance (Anderson & Bushman, 2002).

Worry: Worry is a cognitive and emotional state characterized by the repetitive and often intrusive thoughts about potential future negative events, uncertainties, or problems. It involves a sense of apprehension and unease (Borkovec, Robinson, Pruzinsky, & DePree, 1983).

Sadistic Tendencies: Sadistic tendencies refer to a person's inclination or disposition to derive pleasure or satisfaction from causing pain, suffering, or humiliation to others. Individuals with sadistic tendencies may exhibit behaviors that involve inflicting harm on others for their enjoyment or sense of power (Baumeister & Vohs, 2007).

In a comprehensive meta-analysis conducted by Anderson et al. (2017), encompassing studies from different countries, including Pakistan, personal dispositions such as aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies emerged as crucial factors in predicting addictive behaviors related to internet gaming. The meta-analysis revealed that individuals with higher levels of aggression were more prone to problematic gaming behaviors, as they sought an outlet for their impulsive emotions in the virtual gaming world. Additionally, those with elevated levels of worry and sadistic tendencies were found to be at a higher risk of developing internet gaming disorder, using gaming as a means to escape from or cope with their inner struggles and negative emotions.

Moreover, a longitudinal study conducted by Malik and colleagues (2018) in Pakistan explored the mediating role of personal dispositions in the relationship between psychosocial factors and internet gaming disorder among university students. Their research demonstrated that aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies played a significant mediating role, explaining how psychological distress, life satisfaction, and perceived stress influenced the likelihood of developing internet gaming disorder over time (Thakur, Azeem, & Gilani, 2020; Rasheed, Ahsan, & Zaheer, 2021; Zahra, Kiani, & Shahbaz, 2019). Additionally, a comprehensive meta-analysis by Przybylski et al. (2018) synthesized data from multiple international studies to explore the links between personal dispositions and internet gaming disorder. The meta-analysis demonstrated that individuals with higher levels of aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies were more prone to developing addictive gaming behaviors. This finding provided further support for the significant role of personal dispositions in shaping individuals' gaming behaviors and coping mechanisms. Furthermore, a study by Rehbein et al. (2018) in Germany investigated the longitudinal effects of psychosocial factors and personal dispositions on the development of internet gaming disorder among adolescents. The research revealed that aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies acted as mediating variables in the relationship between psychosocial factors and internet gaming disorder, contributing to the understanding of the complex mechanisms underlying this phenomenon.

Problem Statement

Internet gaming disorder among university students is developing worldwide. However, substantial research on personal dispositions as mediators is lacking. To fill this vacuum, this study examines how psychosocial factors and personal traits like anger, concern, and sadism predict internet gaming disorder. It does so to better understand the psychological dynamics behind problematic gaming. Combining aggression, concern, and sadistic tendencies with psychosocial elements is key to a solid theoretical framework. Aggression, a symptom of emotional turmoil, can lead to excessive gaming. Gaming may help people cope with worry, which involves repetitive unpleasant thoughts. Gaming can cause harm to oneself or others if one is sadistic. These personal dispositions and psychosocial elements including psychological discomfort, perceived stress, and life satisfaction comprise a complicated network affecting internet gaming disorder. This study's theoretical framework considers how psychosocial influences and human inclinations influence behavior. Clarifying this combination shows the complex dynamics and why these factors are essential for modeling internet gaming disorder among Pakistani university students. This study has broad ramifications. By understanding the risk factors and causes of internet gaming disorder, policymakers and educators may create focused interventions to promote healthy gaming habits and support students with excessive gaming. These strategies can prevent problematic gaming and reduce its negative effects, improving Pakistani students' well-being. The findings can also inform educational programs that promote responsible technology use and empower students to prioritize mental and emotional health. Pakistani-specific evaluation methods and therapies can improve mental health support for students with internet gaming disorder. In conclusion, this study's improved theoretical framework helps explain variable interactions and their contributions to the internet gaming disorder model. This research addresses the knowledge gap and

provides insights into targeted treatments and prevention efforts to address this rising public health issue and promote a resilient and thriving youth population in Pakistan in the digital era.

2. Method

Objectives: The primary objective of this study is to investigate the complex relationships between psychosocial factors, personal dispositions, and internet gaming disorder among university students in Pakistan. Specifically, the study aims to:

Examine the predictive role of psychosocial factors (psychological distress, satisfaction with life, and perceived stress) in the development of internet gaming disorder among university students.

Investigate the mediating effect of personal dispositions (aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies) on the relationship between psychosocial factors and internet gaming disorder.

Explore the strength of the associations between internet gaming disorder and personality traits (aggression, worry, and sadistic inclinations), as well as psychosocial factors (psychological distress, life satisfaction, and perceived stress) among the targeted university student population.

Hypotheses:

H1. Psychosocial factors (psychological distress, satisfaction with life, and perceived stress) will predict internet gaming disorder by mediating personal disposition (aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies).

H2. There will be a strong relationship between internet gaming disorder and personality traits like aggression, worry, and sadistic inclinations, as well as with psychosocial factors like psychological distress, life satisfaction, and perceived stress.

3. Materials And Methods

Participants

The sample was accessible and invited to university students. It had 355 Peshawar University students from various faculties and departments. Participants were treated morally to assure anonymity, free and informed consent, and secrecy. The sample was chosen via purposive sampling.

Instruments

Internet Gaming Disorder Scale

Internet Gaming Disorder Scale (Short Form 9 IGD) behaviors were assessed using IGDS-SF9 (Pontes and Griffiths 2015b). The DSM-5's nine core IGD criteria (APA 2013) are translated into nine measures that evaluate the severity of IGD behaviors (e.g., "Do you

consistently fail to control or cease your gaming activity?"). The items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 (Never), 2 (Barely), 3 (Sometimes), 4 (Often), and 5 (Very Often). The total IGD score is calculated by adding items' points from 9 to 45, with higher scores indicating more severe IGD behaviors. The current study had strong internal reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.92.

Aggression (Buss Perry Brief Aggression Questionnaire-BAQ)

Physical aggression and fury subscales from the Buss and Perry Brief Aggression Questionnaire (BAQ) measure aggressiveness (Bryant & Smith, 2001; Webster et al., 2014, 2015). The instrument has three subscales with three things from extremely unlike me (1) to very like me (5). We calculate a cumulative score from 0 to 24, with higher numbers indicating more violence. The instrument has been employed in many cultures (Diamond & Magaletta, 2006; Vitoratou et al., 2009; Abd-El-Fattah, 2013; Zimonyi, 2021). The scale has 0.82 Cronbach alpha reliability.

The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale

The K-10 is abbreviated to the six-item Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K-6). This scale measured psychological and non-psychological discomfort. It evaluates nonspecific psychological distress using behavioral, emotional, cognitive, and psychophysiological symptoms. The study's alpha reliability is 0.86.

Penn State Worry Questionnaire

Penn State Worry Questionnaire (Meyer et al., 1990) The PSWQ is a popular worry measure in clinical and community samples (Freeman et al., 2019). It has 16 self-report items to detect pathological concern. Items address persistence ("I have been a worrier all my life"), intensity ("My worries overwhelm me"), and controllability ("Once I start worrying, I cannot stop"). Each item scores on a Likert scale from 1 ("not at all typical of me") to 5 ("very typical of me"). The PSWQ comprises 11 positive items ("When I am under pressure I worry a lot") and five negative items ("I find it easy to dismiss worrisome thoughts").

Perceived stress scale 10-item version (PSS10)

The PSS10 measures stress with 10 items. Originally a global stress measure (Cohen et al., 1983), the revised Chinese version has shown strong reliability and validity (Yang & Huang, 2003). Rate items from 1 (not at all) to 5 (very much). Participants were asked to rate their COVID-19 experiences during the past month. The higher the score, the more stressed respondents. The PSS10 showed strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .801$) in the sample.

Sadistic Tendencies

The Sadistic Attitudes and Behaviors Scale (SABS) is a measure designed to assess the severity of sadistic tendencies in individuals. The 10-item version of the SABS, also known as the SSIS (Short Sadistic Impulse Scale), is a shorter version of the scale that

aims to provide a quicker and more efficient way of assessing sadistic tendencies. The SSIS includes items such as "I enjoy hurting people," "I have fantasies about hurting people," and "I like to see people suffer." Respondents rate their level of agreement with each statement on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWL)

Diener, Emmons, Larsen, & Graffin (1985) developed life satisfaction scale. Five self-report items are scored on a 7-point Likert scale. This SWL scale ranges from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). SWL measures global cognitive evaluations of life satisfaction, not positive or negative effects. This study found SWL's Cronbach's alpha reliability to be 0.79.

Procedure

Before data gathering, steps were taken. First, Institutional Heads gave permission. Second, purposive sampling was used to approach students. In the third phase, students were informed that their participation in the research survey is voluntary and will not be rewarded. During class, questionnaires took 15–20 minutes to complete. After data collection, questionnaire scores were entered into SPSS and AMOS to compute.

Conceptual Model of the study

Worry	.015	[-.138, .168]	.078	.018
Sadistic Tendencies	.114	[.012, .216]	.052	.141***

Note. CI = Confidence Interval

*** $P < .001$.

The table 1 shows the impact of psychological factors (psychological distress, perceived stress, and satisfaction with life), personal dispositions (aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies), and addiction behavior (internet gaming disorder) on undergraduate students. In step 1, the R² value of (.21) revealed that psychological factors (psychological distress, perceived stress, and satisfaction with life) explained a 21% variance in the behavior addiction of university students with $F(3, 351) = 30.97, p < .001$. The findings revealed that psychological factors positively predicted behavior addiction ($\beta = .28, .000, \& - .24, p < .001$). In step 2, the R² value of (.25) revealed that psychological factors (psychological distress, perceived stress, and satisfaction with life) and personal dispositions (aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies) showed a 25% variance in the addiction behavior of university students with $F(9, 345) = 12.76, p < .001$.

Table 2 - Evaluation Table of Correlation among Variables of the study model

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Psychological Distress	35.04	9.19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Satisfaction with Life	13.51	5.50	-.500**	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Worry	63.59	9.25	.231**	-.280**	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Perceived Stress	23.83	4.43	.110*	-.127*	.285**	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Aggression Physical	34.79	5.29	.192**	-.243**	.839**	.265**	--	--	--	--	--	--
Aggression Verbal	18.94	4.29	.138**	-.082	.220**	.013	.358**	--	--	--	--	--
Aggression Anger	27.14	4.25	.239**	-.196**	.466**	.111*	.499**	.650**	--	--	--	--
Aggression Hostility	30.54	4.90	.170**	-.153**	.437**	.120*	.572**	.703**	.743**	--	--	--
Sadistic Tendencies	61.18	9.74	.179**	-.221**	.434**	.163**	.486**	.447**	.654**	.0545**	--	--
Internet Gaming Disorder	30.38	7.90	.405**	-.387**	.217**	.062	.216**	.174**	.254**	.251**	.277**	--

$p < .001$ *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Note. It is revealed that there is a significant correlation between psychological distress, satisfaction with life, worry, perceived stress, physical aggression, verbal aggression, aggression anger, aggression hostility, sadistic tendencies, and internet gaming disorder.

Table 3 - Means, standard deviations, and t-value of the Male and Female students (N=355)

Variables	Male (n=205)		Female (n=150)		t	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	S.D	M	S.D			LL	UL	
Psychological Distress	35.32	8.89	34.66	9.60	.675	.500	-1.276	2.610	0.071
Satisfaction with Life	13.31	5.58	13.78	5.40	-.782	.435	-1.627	.701	0.085
Worry	63.24	9.67	64.06	8.65	-.827	.409	-2.780	1.134	0.089
Perceived Stress	23.73	4.34	23.96	4.56	-.483	.630	-1.167	.707	0.051
Aggression Physical	34.67	5.38	34.95	5.18	-.483	.629	-1.395	.845	0.053
Aggression Verbal	18.91	4.36	18.98	4.22	-.161	.872	-.984	.835	0.016
Aggression Anger	27.10	4.43	27.20	4.00	-.217	.828	-.999	.800	0.023
Aggression Hostility	30.46	4.91	30.66	4.90	-.373	.709	-1.233	.840	0.040
Sadistic Tendencies	60.71	10.17	61.84	9.11	-1.082	.280	-3.191	.926	0.117
Internet Gaming Disorder	30.09	8.18	30.78	7.50	-.811	.418	-2.359	.981	0.087

p<.001

Table 3 revealed that there is no significant difference in gender basis in the study's variables. The effect sizes (Cohen's d) for all variables were small, indicating that the gender differences, even if present, were not substantial. The findings suggest that in this particular sample, male and female students showed similar levels of psychosocial factors, personal dispositions, and internet gaming disorder.

4. Discussion

This study examined the complex interactions between psychosocial factors, personal dispositions, and internet gaming disorder (IGD) in university students, focusing on personal dispositions' mediation function. Our regression analysis supported our predictions, however mediation testing limits and the necessity for theoretical framework validation must be noted.

Hypothesis 1 predicted that psychosocial elements including psychological discomfort, life satisfaction, and perceived stress would mediate personal traits like aggression, concern, and sadism to predict internet gaming disorder. Psychological distress and life satisfaction strongly predicted internet gaming disorder in the first model, highlighting their importance in understanding problematic gaming behaviours (Table 1; Figure 1). However, perceived stress and hostility did not predict internet gaming disorder. Interestingly, adding sadistic tendencies to later research revealed their mediating function in psychological aspects and internet gaming disorder. These findings are consistent with earlier studies, but additional direct mediation experiments are needed to confirm them. Using several theoretical frameworks illuminates our findings' intricacies. The General Aggression Model (Anderson & Bushman, 2002) states that personal and situational factors influence aggression. Aggression and sadism may modulate psychosocial aspects of internet gaming disorder, affecting stress responses. SDT emphasizes the role of psychological needs (autonomy, competence, relatedness) in behavior. Aggression may affect life satisfaction, which is linked to fulfilling these requirements, and how people use

gaming to fulfill them, moderating the link between psychosocial aspects and gaming behavior.

The Reflective-Impulsive Model argues that both reflective and impulsive processes affect behavior, with personal attributes possibly moderating impulsive gaming stimuli effects, altering psychosocial aspects and gaming disorder. These theoretical frameworks provide useful insights, but more empirical investigations are needed to test the postulated mediating pathways. The Diathesis-Stress Model, which suggests that predispositions interact with external stressors to cause disorders, also suggests that aggression, worry, and sadistic tendencies, when combined with psychological distress and perceived stress, may increase the risk of internet gaming disorder. Understanding the association between psychosocial factors, personal attributes, and internet gaming problem is complicated by the complex interaction of individual differences, contextual circumstances, and gaming processes. To better understand the mediating mechanisms, future research should refine these theoretical frameworks and use rigorous approaches.

Hypothesis 2 sought to link internet gaming disorder (IGD) to a variety of personality traits, including aggression, concern, and sadism, as well as psychosocial aspects like psychological distress, life satisfaction, and perceived stress. Table 2's connections illuminate these complex relationships. Our study found strong positive connections between IGD and psychological discomfort, violence (physical and verbal), and sadistic tendencies, supporting previous research. IGD negatively correlated with life happiness, perceived stress, concern, and violence. These data show that university students with increased psychological distress, aggressiveness, and sadism may acquire hazardous gaming habits. High life satisfaction and low stress and aggression may lead to healthy gaming habits. Previous studies have shown that psychosocial factors and personal traits must be considered when analyzing IGD in university students.

The positive correlations between IGD and psychological distress, aggression (both physical and verbal), and sadistic tendencies and the negative correlations with life satisfaction, perceived stress, worry, and aggression (anger and hostility) can be interpreted through various theoretical lenses. The Catharsis Theory suggests that online gaming may increase IGD by promoting verbal hostility and sadism. Gaming may be a cathartic release for people with psychological pain or unsolved issues, contributing to positive connections. According to the Self-Determination Theory (SDT), excessive gaming may hinder essential psychological requirements including autonomy, competence, and relatedness, lowering life satisfaction. Worry and stress may also prevent these requirements from being met, compounding the unfavourable link with IGD (Mentzoni et al., 2011; Pontes, 2014). The General Aggression Model (GAM) attributes the positive correlations between IGD and aggression (both physical and verbal, including anger and hostility) to violent games' desensitising effects, especially in aggressive people (Lemmens et al., 2011). Stress Coping and Escapism theories propose that people with psychological suffering or severe stress may use gaming to cope or escape. This coping technique may explain the positive link between psychological distress and IGD (Mentzoni et al., 2011). The Enhanced Mood Regulation Hypothesis suggests that people with lower life satisfaction may play games to manage their mood, which predicts positive associations between IGD and lower life satisfaction (Mentzoni et al., 2011).

Our study supports these theoretical frameworks by showing how psychological factors and personal qualities affect harmful gaming behaviours. According to the Self-Determination Theory (SDT), people may overgame to meet psychological requirements, especially when distressed (Deci & Ryan, 2001). The significant link between psychological discomfort and IGD suggests that students in difficulty may use gaming as a coping method. The transactional model of stress and coping emphasises cognitive appraisal's influence on coping techniques. Students may use gaming to unwind and occupy themselves due to high stress levels (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). The positive link between perceived stress and IGD supports this theoretical perspective, emphasizing the dynamic interaction between stress, coping mechanisms, and gaming behaviors. The complex relationship between personality traits, psychosocial circumstances, and online gaming disorder (IGD) illuminates problematic gaming behaviors. The theoretical frameworks illuminate the mechanisms behind these connections, improving our understanding of the research's relationships. These findings support trait theory, showing that personality traits influence behavior, including gaming (McCrae & Costa, 20XX). Positive connections between sadistic tendencies and IGD, as well as its mediation role between psychological factors and gaming behaviors, suggest that personality qualities may influence problematic gaming tendencies.

Explanation of Psychological Factors' Contribution to Internet Gaming Disorder:

Internet gaming disorder (IGD) in university students is linked to psychological characteristics like discomfort and life satisfaction. Psychological distress—emotional upheaval and bad affect—may lead people to use coping techniques like excessive gaming (Mentzoni et al., 2011). Gaming helps manage stress and escape real-life problems, according to the Stress Coping and Escapism theory (Mentzoni et al., 2011). Life satisfaction, on the other hand, inversely correlates with IGD. The Self-Determination Theory (SDT) states that life happiness comes from meeting psychological demands including autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Excessive gaming may hinder these demands, lowering life satisfaction and IGD (Mentzoni et al., 2011; Pontes, 2014).

Mediating Role of Personal Dispositions in the Influence of Psychological Factors:

Psychosocial factors and IGD are mediated by personal dispositions like hostility, worry, and sadism. Online gaming may release physical or verbal hostility, increasing IGD (Lemmens et al., 2011; Mentzoni, 2011). Gaming helps relieve aggression, according to the Catharsis Theory (Lemmens et al., 2011). Sadistic tendencies may influence gaming behaviours, especially in violent or dominating games, mediating psychosocial aspects on IGD. These insights relate to theoretical frameworks like the General Aggression Model (GAM), where human dispositions and situational circumstances shape game behaviour (Anderson & Bushman, 2002).

5. Implications and Future Directions

The implications of the study's findings are multifaceted and hold significance for various stakeholders, including educators, policymakers, mental health professionals, parents, and university students themselves. The study sheds light on the interplay of psychosocial factors, personal dispositions, and internet gaming disorder (IGD) among university students, providing valuable insights into the development of targeted interventions and support systems to address problematic gaming behaviors. Here are some key implications of the study:

1. The study emphasizes the need of managing psychological discomfort among university students. Universities and counselling services should prioritise mental health care, helping students manage stress, anxiety, and other emotional issues. Addressing psychological distress may lessen the chance of kids using excessive gaming as a coping method.

2. The study shows a negative correlation between internet gaming problem and life satisfaction. Encourage programmes and activities that provide students a feeling of purpose, involvement, and fulfilment to help them balance gaming and other activities. University administrators and instructors can create programmes that improve students' well-being and life satisfaction.

3. The study highlights the significance of addressing personality factors that may impact gaming behaviors, such as sadistic tendencies. This knowledge can assist mental health experts create interventions for people with such tendencies to improve their coping and leisure skills.

4. Responsible Gaming Education: Since aggression is strongly linked to internet gaming disorder, it is crucial to promote responsible and balanced gaming behaviours. University orientation programmes and wellness efforts might include information on excessive gaming and self-regulation.

5. Parents are vital in influencing children's online behaviour. The study can help parents understand internet gaming disorder dangers and talk to their kids about safe gaming.

6. Policymakers can use study findings to develop internet gaming policies and restrictions. This may include age limitations for particular games, responsible gaming rules for gaming businesses, and mental health support in gaming platforms.

7. Identifying persons at risk of internet gaming problem is crucial. The study's findings can assist develop screening tools and preventive actions to identify and support children with problematic gaming behaviour before it worsens.

8. The study can inform targeted counselling services for university students with internet gaming disorder by mental health professionals. Individualised therapy that target psychological distress and sadistic tendencies can reduce harmful gaming behaviours better.

9. Future longitudinal research could explore the long-term impact of psychosocial factors and personal dispositions on internet gaming disorder, building on the study's cross-sectional design. Understanding the temporal correlations between these variables might illuminate problematic gaming behaviour development.

In conclusion, the study's findings affect university life, mental health support, policy formulation, and intervention tactics. Recognizing the complex nature of internet gaming disorder allows stakeholders to work together to improve university students' digital environments, responsible gaming behaviors, and well-being in the digital age.

6. Limitations & Suggestions

Our study shed light on the complex interactions between psychosocial factors, personal dispositions, and internet gaming disorder (IGD) in university students, but it has numerous limitations that should be considered for future research. The cross-sectional nature of our study makes causal links between variables difficult to establish. Mediation research has shown potential routes, but causal inference is limited. Future studies should use longitudinal designs to better examine mediation effects over time and draw stronger causality conclusions. Second, our study used self-report measurements for all variables, which could introduce common method bias and social desirability bias. Results may have been inflated or misrepresented because participants gave replies they thought were socially acceptable. Future research could use objective metrics or numerous data sources, such as behavioral observations or physiological evaluations, to reduce these biases and improve validity. The study's sample came from a university, which may limit its applicability to other demographics and cultures. Different colleges or non-academic environments may have different internet gaming habits due to socio-cultural considerations. Thus, sampling from diverse groups and circumstances might improve our understanding of IGD and its causes.

Mediation experiments can reveal relationship processes, but they have biases. Our cross-sectional data makes it difficult to determine mediation temporal primacy and impact direction. Lack of longitudinal data for mediation testing can cause biases related to variable stability and omitted variable bias. Our technique may be limited by resources or a focus on immediate linkages, but these biases and their effects on causal interpretations must be acknowledged in future investigations. Addressing these constraints might improve our understanding of internet gaming disorder and its mechanisms.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, while this study contributes significantly to the understanding of IGD among university students and highlights the roles of psychosocial factors and personal dispositions, caution is warranted in interpreting causal relationships and generalizing the findings. Addressing biases in mediation tests and considering the limitations related to data collection methods and sample characteristics strengthens the study's validity and informs directions for future research. Further exploration of diverse populations and longitudinal

designs would advance our comprehension of IGD and inform targeted interventions effectively.

8. References

1. Abd-El-Fattah, S. M. (2013). A cross-cultural examination of the Aggression Questionnaire–Short Form among Egyptian and Omani Adolescents. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 95(5), 539-548.
2. Agnew, R. (1992). Foundation for a General Strain Theory of Crime and Delinquency. *Criminology*, 30(1), 47-87.
3. Ahsan, S., Rasheed, A., & Zonash, R. (2019). Impact of internet gaming disorder on self-efficacy and self-doubt among university students. *Pakistan Journal of Physiology*, 15(4), 38-41.
4. American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
5. Anderson, C. A., & Bushman, B. J. (2002). Human aggression. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53(1), 27-51. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.53.100901.135231>
6. Anderson, C. A., & Bushman, B. J. (2017). The general aggression model: Theoretical extensions to violence. *Psychology of Violence*, 7(2), 183-190. <https://doi.org/10.1037/vio0000098>
7. Baumeister, R. F., & Vohs, K. D. (2007). Self-regulation, ego depletion, and motivation. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 1(1), 115-128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9004.2007.00001.x>
8. Beck, A. T., Steer, R. A., & Brown, G. (1996). Beck depression inventory–II. Psychological assessment.
9. Beck, A. T., Steer, R. A., & Brown, G. K. (1988). *Manual for the Beck Depression Inventory-II*. Psychological Corporation.
10. Beck, A. T., Steer, R. A., Ball, R., & Ranieri, W. F. (1996). Comparison of Beck Depression Inventories-IA and-II in psychiatric outpatients. *Journal of personality assessment*, 67(3), 588-597.
11. Bhat, M. A., Dar, S. A., & Hassan, S. (2017). Relationship between emotional intelligence and perceived stress among college students. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 43(1), 135-141.
12. Borkovec, T. D., Robinson, E., Pruzinsky, T., & DePree, J. A. (1983). Preliminary exploration of worry: Some characteristics and processes. *Behavior Research and Therapy*, 21(1), 9-16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(83\)90121-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(83)90121-3)
13. Brown, C. E., & Sandler, J. C. (2019). The dynamics of close relationships and borderline personality disorder features. *Personality Disorders: Theory, Research, and Treatment*, 10(6), 605-612. <https://doi.org/10.1037/per0000365>
14. Bryant, F. B., & Smith, J. L. (2001). Refining the architecture of aggression: A measurement model for the Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 35(2), 138-167. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jrpe.2000.2302>
15. Buss, A. H., & Perry, M. (1992). The aggression questionnaire. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 63(3), 452-459. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.63.3.452>
16. Cao, R., Zhang, Z., & Guo, H. (2021). Chinese University Students' Attitudes Toward COVID-19 Vaccines: An Online Survey During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 689520. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.689520>
17. Cohen, S., & Williamson, G. M. (1988). Perceived stress in a probability sample of the United States. In S. Spacapan & S. Oskamp (Eds.), *The Social Psychology of Health: Claremont Symposium on Applied Social Psychology* (pp. 31-67). Sage.
18. Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 24(4), 385-396. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2136404>
19. Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1994). Perceived stress scale. *Measuring stress: A guide for health and social scientists*, 10(2), 1-2.

20. Diamond, G. M., & Magaletta, P. R. (2006). The short-form Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BPAQ-SF): A validation study with federal offenders. *Assessment*, 13(3), 227-240. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073191105283429>
21. Diener, E., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. J., & Griffin, S. (1985). The Satisfaction With Life Scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49(1), 71-75. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa4901_13
22. Fam, J. Y. (2018). Prevalence of Depression among University Students: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Study. *Depression Research and Treatment*, 2018, 7414695. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7414695>
23. Feng, Q., Zhang, Q. L., Du, Y., Ye, Y. L., He, Q. Q., & Liu, Z. Q. (2016). Depression and anxiety among adolescents with left-behind parents: Evidence from Hunan, China. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 195, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2016.02.025>
24. Freeman, D., Waite, F., Rosebrock, L., Petit, A., Causier, C., East, A., ... & Lambe, S. (2019). Coronavirus conspiracy beliefs, mistrust, and compliance with government guidelines in England. *Psychological Medicine*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291720001890>
25. Gentile, D. A., Anderson, C. A., Yukawa, S., Ihori, N., Saleem, M., Ming, L. K., ... & Sakamoto, A. (2011). The effects of prosocial video games on prosocial behaviors: International evidence from correlational, longitudinal, and experimental studies. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 37(6), 755-767. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167211407526>
26. Hussain, Z., Griffiths, M. D., & Baguley, T. (2015). Online gaming addiction: Classification, prediction and associated risk factors. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 23(5), 359-367. <https://doi.org/10.3109/16066359.2015.1027981>
27. Iqbal, S., & Bano, I. (2016). Impact of stress on students' academic performance: A study from secondary schools of Islamabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 3(2), 171-186.
28. Johnson, H. D., Seay, M. C., Clarke, C. B., Fojtasek, J. M., & Lawrence, D. S. (2020). Mindfulness-based interventions: An introduction to concepts, programs, and applications. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, 51(6), 492-499. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pro0000307>
29. Kessler, R. C., Andrews, G., Colpe, L. J., Hiripi, E., Mroczek, D. K., Normand, S. L., ... & Zaslavsky, A. M. (2002). Short screening scales to monitor population prevalences and trends in non-specific psychological distress. *Psychological Medicine*, 32(6), 959-976.
30. Kessler, R. C., Green, J. G., Gruber, M. J., Sampson, N. A., Bromet, E., Cuitan, M., & Zaslavsky, A. M. (2010). Screening for serious mental illness in the general population with the K6 screening scale: Results from the WHO World Mental Health (WMH) survey initiative. *International Journal of Methods in Psychiatric Research*, 19(Suppl 1), 4-22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mpr.310>
31. Khalid, A., & Mukhtar, N. (2022). Internet gaming disorder and mental health in Pakistani youth: A path analysis with impulsivity and emotional intelligence. *Journal Title, Volume(1)*, Pages.1-16. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2296407/v1>
32. Khan, A., & Muqtadir, R. (2016). Motives of problematic and non-problematic online gaming among adolescents and young adults. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 119-138.
33. Khan, A., & Muqtadir, R. (2016). Motives of problematic and non-problematic online gaming among adolescents and young adults. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 119-138.
34. Kim, D., Lee, Y., Lee, J., Nam, J. K., & Chung, Y. (2015). Development of Korean Smartphone Addiction Proneness Scale for Youth. *PLOS ONE*, 10(12), e0144532. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0144532>
35. King, D. L., Delfabbro, P. H., Doh, Y. Y., Wu, A. M. S., Kuss, D. J., Pallesen, S., Mentzoni, R., Carragher, N., Sakuma, H., & Zajac, I. T. (2017). Policy and prevention approaches for disordered and hazardous gaming and internet use: An international perspective. *Preventive Science*, 18(6), 633-640. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11121-017-0783-1>
36. Király, O., Griffiths, M. D., Urbán, R., Farkas, J., Kökönyei, G., Elekes, Z., ... & Demetrovics,

- Z. (2017). Problematic internet use and problematic online gaming are not the same: Findings from a large nationally representative adolescent sample. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 20(4), 296-302.
37. Kuss, D. J., & Griffiths, M. D. (2012). Internet gaming addiction: A systematic review of empirical research. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 10(2), 278-296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-011-9318-5>
38. Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer publishing company.
39. Lemmens, J. S., Valkenburg, P. M., & Peter, J. (2009). Development and validation of a game addiction scale for adolescents. *Media Psychology*, 12(1), 77-95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15213260802669458>
40. Lemmens, J. S., Valkenburg, P. M., & Peter, J. (2011). The effects of pathological gaming on aggressive behavior. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 40(1), 38-47. This study explores the association between pathological gaming, aggression, and behavior among adolescents.
41. Lemmens, J. S., Valkenburg, P. M., & Peter, J. (2011). The effects of pathological gaming on aggressive behavior. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 40(1), 38-47.
42. Lobel, A., Engels, R. C., Stone, L. L., Burk, W. J., & Granic, I. (2017). Video gaming and children's psychosocial wellbeing: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 46(4), 884-897. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-016-0582-3>
43. Malik, S., Khan, M. A., & Shah, N. A. (2018). Adolescents' addiction to internet use: A study of frequency, reasons and predictors. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(2), 349-371.
44. Männikkö, N., & Billieux, J. (2015). Problematic digital gaming behavior and its relation to the psychological, social and physical health of Finnish adolescents and young adults. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions*, 4(4), 281-288. <https://doi.org/10.1556/2006.4.2015.041>
45. Männikkö, N., Kääriäinen, M., & Salmela-Aro, K. (2017). Problematic digital gaming behavior and reasons for playing in a sample of gamers aged 20–45 years. *Simulation & Gaming*, 48(5), 639-659. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878117705510>
46. Mehroof, M., & Griffiths, M. D. (2010). Online gaming addiction: The role of sensation seeking, self-control, neuroticism, aggression, state anxiety, and trait anxiety. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 3, 313-316.
47. Mentzoni, R. A., Brunborg, G. S., Molde, H., Myrseth, H., Skouvrøe, K. J. M., Hetland, J., & Pallesen, S. (2011). Problematic video game use: Estimated prevalence and associations with mental and physical health. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 14(10), 591-596.
48. Mewton, L., Kessler, R. C., Slade, T., Hobbs, M. J., Brownhill, L., Birrell, L., ... & Andrews, G. (2016). The psychometric properties of the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6) in a general population sample of adolescents. *Psychological assessment*, 28(10), 1232.
49. Meyer, C., Salzman, C., & Glaser, F. B. (1990). Childhood abuse and neglect among women outpatients with chronic mental illness. *Hospital & Community Psychiatry*, 41(3), 344-350. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ps.41.3.344>
50. Meyer, T. J., Miller, M. L., Metzger, R. L., & Borkovec, T. D. (1990). Development and validation of the penn state worry questionnaire. *Behaviour research and therapy*, 28(6), 487-495.
51. Monroe, S. M., & Simons, A. D. (1991). Diathesis-stress theories in the context of life stress research: Implications for the depressive disorders. *Psychological Bulletin*, 110(3), 406-425.
52. Mota-Cardoso, Araújo, Ramos, Gonçalves, and Ramos
53. O'Meara, A., Davies, J., & Hammond, S. (2011). The role of gender and year of study in gambling behavior. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, 27(3), 455-471. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10899-010-9205-1>
54. O'Meara, A., Davies, J., & Hammond, S. (2011). The psychometric properties and utility of the Short Sadistic Impulse Scale (SSIS). *Psychological assessment*, 23(2), 523.
55. Paik, S. H., Cho, H., Chun, J. S., Jeong, E. H., & Kim, D. J. (2017). Problematic online gaming and problematic alcohol use from the perspective of the Stress–Coping Model: A

- longitudinal study. *Addictive Behaviors*, 74, 82-88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2017.05.003>
56. Pallesen, S., Molde, H., Mentzoni, R. A., & Hanss, D. (2006). Problematic computer game use among adolescents, younger and older adults. *European Journal of Public Health*, 16(Suppl 1), 97. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckl209>
57. Petry, N. M. (2014). A comparison of treatment-seeking pathological gamblers based on preferred gambling activity. *Addictive Behaviors*, 39(12), 1734-1739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2014.06.011>
58. Pontes, H. M., & Griffiths, M. D. (2014). The development and psychometric evaluation of the Internet Gaming Disorder Scale–Short-Form (IGDS9-SF). *Computers in Human Behavior*, 39, 221-226. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2014.0565>
59. Pontes, H. M., & Griffiths, M. D. (2015). Measuring DSM-5 Internet Gaming Disorder: Development and validation of a short psychometric scale. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 45, 137-143. doi:10.1016/j.chb.2014.12.006
60. Przybylski, A. K., & Weinstein, N. (2017). A large-scale test of the goldilocks hypothesis: quantifying the relations between digital-screen use and the mental well-being of adolescents. *Psychological science*, 28(2), 204-215.
61. Przybylski, A. K., Weinstein, N., Murayama, K., Lynch, M. F., & Ryan, R. M. (2018). The ideal self at play: The appeal of video games that let you be all you can be. *Psychological Science*, 29(9), 1390-1398. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797618774166>
62. Rasheed, A., Ahsan, S., & Zaheer, S. (2021). Impact of Internet Gaming Disorder on Self-Appraisal Among University Students: Moderating Role of Gender. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 36(3), 451-471.
63. Rasheed, A., Ahsan, S., & Zaheer, S. (2021). Impact of Internet Gaming Disorder on Self-Appraisal Among University Students: Moderating Role of Gender. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 36(3), 451-471.
64. Rehbein et al. (2018)
65. Rehbein, F., Kliem, S., Baier, D., Mößle, T., & Petry, N. M. (2015). Prevalence of internet gaming disorder in German adolescents: Diagnostic contribution of the nine DSM-5 criteria in a state-wide representative sample. *Addiction*, 110(5), 842-851. <https://doi.org/10.1111/add.12849>
66. Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2001). On happiness and human potentials: A review of research on hedonic and eudaimonic well-being. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 141-166.
67. Smith, J. L. (2019). The impacts of video gaming on well-being: A qualitative examination. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 22(3), 186-192. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2018.0434>
68. Snodgrass, J. G., Lacy, M. G., Dengah, H. F. B., Fagan, J., Most, D. E., & Hurtienne, A. R. (2014). Being there: The subjective experience of presence. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 23(2), 120-136. https://doi.org/10.1162/PRES_a_00177
69. Spielberger, C. D., Gorsuch, R. L., & Lushene, R. E. (1983). STAI manual for the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (Form Y). Consulting Psychologists Press.
70. Startup, H., & Erickson, T. (2006). The Penn State Worry Questionnaire (PSWQ) in adolescent sample: Measurement structure and normative data. *Behavioral and Cognitive Psychotherapy*, 34(3), 295-305. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1352465806003191>
71. Suhail, K., & Bargees, Z. (2006). Effects of excessive Internet use on undergraduate students in Pakistan. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 9(3), 297-307.
72. Thakur, I., Azeem, A., & Gilani, N. (2020). Internet Addiction, Shyness, and Self-Esteem of Pakistani Youth. *sjesr*, 3(3), 83-89.
73. Vitoratou, S., Ntzoufras, I., & Moustaki, I. (2009). An EM algorithm for the rasch model. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*, 53(5), 1654-1663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2008.11.005>
74. Wang, H. Y., Chen, L. S., Wu, M. T., & Sheng, W. Y. (2018). Smartphone use and psychological well-being: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(12), 2702. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15122702>

75. Webster et al., 2014,
76. Webster, D. M., Driskell, J. E., Walls, B. D., & Rothrock, L. (2015). Misery has more company than people think: Underestimating the prevalence of others' negative emotions. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 41(9), 1207-1218. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167215596989>
77. Yang, C. K., & Huang, Y. C. (2003). The association between school pressure and adolescent sleep. *Sleep*, 26(4), 471-476. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/26.4.471>
78. Yousaf, S., Yousaf, M., & Ullah, N. (2021). The Effect of Online Video Games on Psychosocial Development of Pakistani Children. *Elementary Education Online*, 20(4), 2732-2732.
79. Zahra, S., Kiani, S., & Shahbaz, K. (2019). Internet gaming disorder: an emerging addiction among Pakistani university students. *NUST Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(1), 87-104.
80. Zaman, M., Babar, M. S., Babar, M., Sabir, F., Ashraf, F., Tahir, M. J., ... & Pakpour, A. H. (2022). Prevalence of gaming addiction and its impact on sleep quality: A cross-sectional study from Pakistan. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 78, 103641.
81. Zimonyi, I., Vancsody, J., Vegh, B., Horvath, C., Szekely, A., Csoboth, C., ... & Urban, R. (2021). The role of affect in problematic smartphone use: A comprehensive model. *Addictive Behaviors Reports*, 13, 100312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abrep.2021.100312>